

OPPORTUNITIES FOR FORMING PROFESSIONAL CULTURE IN FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Annotation. *This article reveals the possibilities of formation of professional culture in future physical education teachers. Also, the article highlights the situations that athletes should pay attention to in physical education lessons, the inextricable connection between physical culture and aesthetic education. The history of sports and physical education is reviewed. The article analyzes the principles that are important for athletes.*

Key words: *Educational system, physical education, physical culture, aesthetic education, future teacher, harmony, form, rhythm, dynamics, softness, plasticity, fine movement, refinement, restraint, effort, strength, speed, risk, precision, sense of time, technique, strategy, tactics, competition, victory, enjoyment.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье раскрываются возможности формирования профессиональной культуры у будущих учителей физического воспитания. Также в статье освещаются ситуации, на которые следует обращать внимание спортсменам на уроках физической культуры, неразрывная связь физической культуры и эстетического воспитания. Рассмотрена история спорта и физического воспитания. В статье анализируются принципы, важные для спортсменов.*

Ключевые слова: *Система образования, физическое воспитание, физическая культура, эстетическое воспитание, будущий учитель, гармония, форма, ритм, динамика, мягкость, пластичность, мелкие движения, утонченность, сдержанность, усилие, сила, скорость, риск, точность, чувство времени, техника, стратегия, тактика, конкуренция, победа, удовольствие.*

Анотация. *Ушбу мақолада бўлажак жисмоний тарбия ўқитувчиларида касбий маданиятни шакллантириши имкониятлари очиб берилган. Шунингдек, мақолада жисмоний тарбия дарсларида спортчилар эътибор қаратишлари*

лозим бўлган ҳолатлар, жисмоний маданият ва эстетик тарбия орасидаги узвий боғлиқлик, алоқадорлик ёритилган. Спорт ва жисмоний тарбия тарихига назар ташланган. Мақолада спортчилар учун муҳим бўлган принциплар таҳлил қилинган.

Таянч сўзлар: Таълим тизими, жисмоний тарбия, жисмоний маданият, эстетик тарбия, бўлажак ўқитувчи, гармония, шакл, ритм, динамика, майинлик, пластика, нозик ҳаракат, нафосат, вазминлик, зўр бериш, кучлилик, тезлик, таваккалчилик, аниқлик, вақт ҳисси, техника, стратегия, тактика, мусобақа, галаба, завқланиш.

It should not be forgotten that physical culture is created by the people. Forms, methods, and tools of physical education were formed during the initial labor activity. In the process of work, a person has been developing his physical and spiritual strength.

The need for human preparation for life, first of all, for work, historically justified the emergence and further development of physical culture.

Playful activities in the initial period of the development of society were considered an important means of labor education and physical education together with it. Since ancient times, modern types of sports have been carefully preserved and improved for many centuries. These include wrestling, boxing, weightlifting, fencing, swimming, skiing and skating, equestrian sports, football, etc. Each of them is an example of beauty and perfection, harmony of movements, general aesthetics of one or another type of sport. During the development of society, sports projectiles appeared: balls, balls, sticks, clubs, etc.; bars, bars, bars, etc.; rooms, grounds were equipped, stadiums were built.

Tournaments, contests, competitions, sports holidays, Olympics have become traditional. Equipment, sports halls, arenas, stadiums, scenarios of sports events have always been and still are distinguished by the national color of their country, high aesthetic taste corresponding to their time (Ancient Greece, Ancient Rome, sports competitions and tournaments in the East).

The essence of the following terms used in the aesthetic assessment of sports should be emphasized. They are: harmony, form, rhythm and dynamics, smoothness and plasticity, delicate movement, elegance, restraint, giving strength, strength and power, speed and risk, accuracy, sense of time, technique, strategy and tactics, competition - victory, pleasure, etc.

Harmony - flexibility of the body, stature, beauty of the moving body; the overall unity, harmony and proportion of parts is the combination of certain elements of a whole exercise that creates a harmonious whole. For example, in gymnastics - this is a

combination of aesthetic elements (slow, fast); when performing the whole exercise, it is manifested in the combination of small elements with different rhythms of movement.

The form that causes pleasure is the image; appearance, configuration, structure, structure, integrity and unity; composition or style of performance; a way to achieve a goal - beauty, grace and spectacle (for example, in rhythmic gymnastics): especially when soft lines are combined into a complex combination, it gives a special flavor.

Rhythm - form of expressive movement; a style of self-expression (as in dance); integral sign of a single output; gives it completeness, completeness and unity; this is again pattern density, speed variation; in gymnastics - proportionality, consistency of successive elements and their combinations; coordination of movements with the rhythm of music tracking.

Dynamics - movement under the influence of applied forces; line and shape in a sequence of movements.

Softness is an indicator of expressive movement; looks for elegance, grace; poetess and

will have an aesthetic meaning.

Plastic (smoothness) is the structure of the human body; directly watched; causes aesthetic feeling, aesthetic appreciation; athletes convey their feelings to the audience with their actions; it appears both in dynamics and also in statics.

Elegance - charm, gracefulness - beauty of movements, the variety of beauty embodied in posture and posture.

Latofat - beauty of shapes, lines, proportionality of form, polishedness, subtlety of movements, elegance, elegance; striving for smoothness in the conditions of maximum tension in sports (ice dancing, ice skating).

Composure - mental composure, physical capabilities of the athlete; self and situation management; the skill of maintaining composure in a complex game situation is especially unaccustomed

in circumstances; creates an exciting and beautiful scene; the ability to maintain composure even when losing and in controversial and unexpected situations is also an element of beauty in sports.

Performance is the use of one athlete, the energy of the whole team ("team spirit"); requires analysis of movement taking into account weight, area, fluidity; of course, it is necessary to use dynamic abilities; the enjoyment of this effort is felt as an aesthetic value.

Strength is beauty; strength - power - speed - danger - accuracy = basic concepts of beauty in sports. In this case, strength is physical capabilities; power is the product

of strength and speed (the beauty of power); speed - if it is perfect, as a criterion of beauty; it has a wonderful effect of "balancing elements" (skating: a person moves with the power of his own body - this is a huge attraction.

The swiftness of the athlete's movements is artistically skillful, and together with precision, it acquires an additional beauty worthy of even higher appreciation; in the process, the audience is overwhelmed with emotions.

Speed and risk – climbs at controlled speeds (such as downhill skiing) are beautiful; connection of speed with danger, danger; the athlete always moves in tension, but the audience does not see it and therefore enjoys it, exclaiming "Excellent!".

Power is the work (movement) performed per unit of time; performed in sports exercises; evaluation criteria in sports; In sports, maintaining good balance or staying in balance leads the athlete to victory.

Balance is a sign of a highly skilled athlete; dynamic strength (which gymnasts try to hide); The relationship between strength and balance, a well-balanced, powerful form in sports that requires tremendous physical effort to achieve success in many sports, seems to be a mysterious beauty.

Accuracy - correctness combined with control; timing and self-control are at the highest level of sport.

Control is related to the athlete's weapons and self-control, the skill of using his equipment and considering them as his aesthetic perfection, on which a successful and beautiful result depends, self-expression.

A sense of timing is related to self-control, synchronicity of movements in sports aesthetics; the higher the skill of the athlete, the more developed is the sense of timing (shooting, golf, archery - the beauty of ballistics).

Performance technique is an important criterion for evaluating the athlete's performances; it is not only mechanical accuracy, but also the skill of reversing movements - the key to understanding artistry. For example, aesthetic potential grows in gymnastics.

Techniques - methods, actions are performed in the conditions of resistance of opponents, therefore, their implementation is particularly complicated.

Attack - its purpose: to leave fractions of a second for the opponent to think emotionally; enjoyment of an unexpected situation is one of the aesthetic criteria. This is the moment of perfection, which means aesthetics; in the presence of experience and skill, the attack gives pleasure to the athlete and the spectator.

In sports, the goal and its achievement require strength and risk. The most important thing

– confidence, however, it comes with experience.

Experience is the ability to correctly assess the level of risk, self-control. Only then will the completion of the athlete's performance be guaranteed. This gives the viewer a feeling of enjoying sports aesthetics and beauty. In some types of sports, the increase in aesthetic impression is enhanced by the wind. For example, sailing sports, parachuting sports, gliding sports.

In response to external influences, the athlete's sense of his inner strength helps him to examine the surrounding situation and conditions. Such effects are another expression of pleasure through exertion.

Defense - creativity in the game of defense is manifested in the form of beauty, practical impact.

Strategy - if the athlete covers all the happenings as a whole, if he finds the assigned action in advance, if he separates the elements necessary for its implementation, all this is a strategy.

Tactics - requiring a certain degree of advanced thinking justified by the sport specification; moments (of the game) that have an impressive character, are distinguished by the speed of thought, are important in various sports games and one-on-one, formed into a whole - a real strategic art that enhances the aesthetics of the game. Tactics - externalize the individual and collective actions of players and teams aimed at winning over the opponent. It is based on teamwork, characterized by high consciousness and creative initiative in the actions of each player; characterized by active offensive actions supported by an active solid defense. It means attack, defense, resistance to the opponent, victory due to high skill. Tactics are continuously improved, especially during preparation for international competitions.

Competition - pace and rhythm play an important role in this. If the winner has priority in front of an opponent of equal strength - aesthetic peaks are reached. The game itself is perceived in the form of a sense of pleasure as an aesthetic object, until it reaches its peak, which starts from the one-on-one confrontation of worthy opponents, which gradually grows and turns into victory or defeat for one of them. Unexpected events, methods, transitions in the game are noteworthy.

Competitiveness is the most important basis of beauty and excellence in sports. The main thing is that athletes and organizers of sports competitions understand the role of sports as a source of beauty in achieving excellence.

In conclusion, it should be noted that such situations as harmony, equal submission, diversity in sports do not cause special tension in the athlete, but are perceived more sensitively by the audience.

References:

1. Исмаилов Т.У. Педагогические особенности физического воспитания и оздоровительных мероприятий в начальных классах: Автореф.дисс. ... канд.пед.наук. – Т., 2010. – 21 с.
2. Кадыров Р.Х. Народные подвижные игры как средство совершенствования уроков физической культуры // Сборник тезисов научно-практической конференции «Возрождение национальных видов спорта, народных игр и пути широкого использования в физическом воспитании населения». – Ташкент-Джизак, 1991. – С. 63-64.
3. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). РОЛЬ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МОТИВАЦИИ.
4. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS Anvar Takhirovich Hasanov JDPU. "Physical culture" faculty.
5. Atamurodov, Shodiyor. (2023). ТУРИСТИК САЁХАТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ.
6. Nomozov, Abdurashid. (2023). Sog‘lom turmush tarziga sportning ahamiyati hamda o‘rni qanchalik muhimligini ta’sir etuvchi omillari..
7. Buriboyev, Alisher. (2023). Komil inson tarbiyasida jismoniy madaniyatning o‘rni.
8. Yakhshilikov, S. (2023). UNAVOIDABLE CLASHES: EXPLORING THE IMPLICATIONS OF A CHINA-RUSSIA ALLIANCE ON GLOBAL GEOPOLITICS. AUSTRAL: Brazilian Journal of Strategy & International Relations, 12(23). <https://doi.org/10.22456/2238-6912.131366>